

IMPROVEMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN'S SPEECH AND LANGUAGE SKILLS

Saidova Mukhayyo Nuriddin qizi

Samarkand State institute of foreign language, student.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10477403>

Abstract. Preschoolers who struggle with speech and language issues and poor communication development require a great deal of assistance. The interactionistic study sought to determine whether and how reading aloud to youngsters and telling stories could improve their communicative development. The findings demonstrated the frequent use of storytelling and reading aloud, and the staff's conviction that the activity would support the children's conceptual and verbal development was supported by the data. However, this assumes that the preschool staff values literacy and is knowledgeable about using storytelling and reading aloud to enhance kids' communication skills.

Keywords: Foreign language, words, phonetics, rule, methodology, multimedia, preschool children, speech and language development, communication, reading aloud, storytelling, improvements in preschool and school, preschool curriculum, kindergartens in China, creative games, preschools in Sweden.

Introduction

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ РЕЧЕВЫХ И ЯЗЫКОВЫХ НАВЫКОВ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. Дошкольникам с речевыми и языковыми проблемами и плохим коммуникативным развитием требуется большая помощь. Интеракционистское исследование было направлено на то, чтобы определить, может ли чтение вслух подросткам и рассказывание историй улучшить их коммуникативное развитие. подтверждается данными. Однако это предполагает, что персонал дошкольного учреждения ценит грамотность и знает, как использовать рассказывание историй и чтение вслух для улучшения коммуникативных навыков детей.

Ключевые слова: Иностраный язык, слова, фонетика, правило, методика, мультимедиа, дошкольники, речевое и языковое развитие, общение, чтение вслух, рассказывание историй, совершенствование дошкольных и школьных занятий, дошкольная программа, детские сады в Китае, творческие игры, дошкольные учреждения в Швеции.

Введение

Critical domains of child development include speech, language, and communication. They have a crucial role in many aspects of our life, supporting us in thinking and learning, solving issues, building relationships, expressing our basic wants and emotions, and understanding the world around us. Along with this, they also promote the development of many other areas, such as reading, social, and cognitive skills.

Learning a foreign language has evolved over the past several years from a method of self-improvement to a necessity. In many other pre-school educational institutions as well as in schools and colleges, learning a foreign language has become an essential and structural

component of education.

Teaching children is an extremely challenging task that calls for a totally different methodological approach than teaching adults and schoolchildren. It does not follow that an adult who speaks a foreign language is qualified to instruct others in it. When children are taught a foreign language in an ineffective fashion, they may develop a long-term hatred for it and lose faith in their own skills. Preschoolers should only be worked with by qualified experts.

The objectives for preschoolers' language development.

In short, the preschool language learning and development goals are as follows:

- to be able to differentiate shades of meaning in concepts, •to develop the ability to listen, reflect, and express their own views,
- to develop their use of spoken language, vocabulary, and concepts, ask questions, argue, and communicate with others,
- to develop an interest in written language, understand symbols, pictures, texts, and different media, and to develop their creative abilities.

The goals are not intended to be used for assessing children's development or learning. They are largely aimed at the preschool personnel and are targets to strive toward. In the early stages of learning English, children gradually build the fundamentals of communicative competence, which comprise the following aspects:

- mastering, strengthening, and activating English vocabulary;
- mastering a certain number of basic grammatical structures;
- being able to repeat English words phonetically and after the teacher or speaker, thereby gradually forming listening attention, phonetic hearing, and correct pronunciation.

Teaching English to preschoolers is unique in that it involves more than just having them sit at a table and leaf through books and notebooks. Children should strive for information on their own, and the process shouldn't be tedious. Youngsters communicate in short terms, have clear thinking, and accept things literally. When a teacher teaches something, he should be explicit and provide an example. English is thus a game for young children. This is the only way to get good results and develop a child's positive attitude toward learning a foreign language in order to build a relationship.

The foundation of game approach is having a child or teacher create an imaginative scenario and take on a certain role.

Any traditional games, like dances with a variety of partners, that enhance phonetic and rhythm-melodic aspects of speech and allow you to fully immerse yourself in the language are considered rhythmic music games. Some examples of these games are "Nuts and may," "What's your name?" "I like my friends," "Heard, shoulders, knees, and toes," and others.

Artistic or creative games. The youngster walks the path to this kind of activity—which is situated between play and artistic creation—through the game. Playing creative games encourages a child's imagination to grow.

Additionally, one crucial approach to teaching kids a foreign language is the utilization of multimedia resources. As a result, when learning a foreign language, kids struggle to grasp the meaning of the cartoon's words but yet manage to grasp them through the characters' actions. For kids, it's an enjoyable and efficient method of language acquisition.

In modern China, multimedia equipment is installed in every kindergarten. Through music, poetry, stories, and movies, kids can learn the English language. It makes dull language instruction enjoyable every day. Each kindergarten class in China consists of roughly ten pupils, and the teacher employs a teaching strategy that takes into account the individual psychology of each youngster. In order to accomplish this, the teacher needs to be a competent psychotherapist, musician, artist, foreign language instructor, and mother. It goes without saying that in this day and age of development, the Chinese are building excellent facilities for the next generation.

Teachers have a lot of chances when they use multimedia to teach. It is therefore possible to pique children's curiosity and hold their attention for an extended period of time. This shows us that kids' language skills have improved once more.

In preschools where storytelling and reading aloud were the primary teaching strategies, the Swedish study examined how preschoolers' speech and language growth improved. The authors' primary objective is to investigate the impact of storytelling and read aloud as a teaching and motivational strategy on the communication skills of kids with speech and language problems.

For this study, eleven cities elementary schools in Sweden were selected as learning environments because they offered children a natural setting in which to acquire language and communication skills through social and cultural interaction. Using a "yes" or "no" or cannot determine assessment, preschool educators were questioned about the fiction and nonfiction they used with their students. Two stages of data collection took place in 2012 and 2013. 573 kids between the ages of 1 and 5 from 18 different countries, speaking diverse languages and ethnicities, made up the student body.

According to the survey's findings, every preschool that took part in 2012 and a follow-up study in 2013 stated that they read aloud to their students every day—in most cases, multiple times a day. Storytelling was employed by six preschool educational institutions in 2012 and by seventeen in 2013. Teachers also mentioned that kids might write their own stories and use their own language to express themselves.

As instructional strategies to effectively assist communication development, the study's findings emphasized the value of storytelling and reading aloud. It was evident from the results that children's everyday activities and routines changed for the better when they achieved goals related to communication. Children's interest in signs, symbols, pictures, and letters grow via storytelling and reading aloud, and their vocabulary and language comprehension increase.

Despite their prior knowledge of the benefits of storytelling and reading aloud to children, preschool teachers were able to better understand the value of daily practice and develop skills that would enable them to support children in communication, even when there are delays or distortions.

Methods of teaching English to preschool children.

Task-oriented methodology

When teaching English, the task-based method separates students' abilities and competences to teach them the things they genuinely need to know to accomplish their goals and objectives.

The assignments In this approach ought to be predicated on typical real-life scenarios that

students can run into, such as vacationing, conversing with foreigners in a hotel, airport, or dining establishment. Teaching students how to place an order at a restaurant, reserve a hotel room, or perhaps tackle more difficult assignments like reviewing a play for the stage would be an example of a task-based approach. This method puts the task at hand before the language that is taught, rather than the other way around.

Teachers that use this method must have a thorough understanding of the needs and expectations of their pupils. It is impossible to create lessons that will support pupils in succeeding in certain circumstances without it.

The question "why am I teaching my students English?" should always be asked by educators who choose to employ the task-based method. The response to that query will aid in creating a strong curriculum that appeals to kids.

Interactive methods

Teaching English to adults and children requires a strong emphasis on interactive learning. You and your child can engage in a variety of activities that will benefit you both. Use your imagination. Make a poster or collage, engage in crafts, etc. Additionally, you can plan workshops where you and your child make soft toys, bake pizza, make salads, or engage in any other activity. For instance, it can involve creating a flower bed, a mini-garden, or flower gardens.

A teacher's (or parent's) interaction with a child in English should always occur during live communication and real-life situations. With the use of numerous activities, this technique facilitates the indirect language learning of both adults and children.

Theatricalization or dramatization

Theater in English is many teachers' favorite teaching method and many students favorite activity. Kids get especially immersed in the world of brave princes and princesses, evil witches and good fairies, magical creatures and talking animals. Kids are quickly drawn into the plot and easily remember the events, favorite characters, and their catchphrases.

At first, a teacher can read a fairy tale and discuss it with the students, look at the pictures or watch a cartoon, learn the keywords and then "narrate" the fairy tale later. But what kids love the most is to watch performances of their favorite scenes or tales with puppets, screens and decorations.

Preparing for a play immerses students into the English-speaking environment and a more natural use of language. That's why the "immersion method" when kids are being spoken to in English right away helps develop their language skills, comprehension and contextual guessing in English. And this is exactly why it is so popular among educators who teach English to kids.

Spaced repetition technique

Spaced repetition is a technique that focuses on increasing intervals between previously learned and acquired material to retain maximum information. It can be successfully used in teaching both kids and adults.

According to scientific reports, it works mostly because frequent repetition helps our memory maintain existing knowledge. Once we learn something new, systematic revision at intervals helps us remember a more significant percentage of the material.

To make this teaching method work, you need to practice the previously learned vocabulary, phrases or grammar rules with increasing intervals. At first, it can be an hour, then a

day, then once a week, then monthly etc. If you recognize a new piece of English information right away – you know it already very well. If not, you need to keep reviewing it more often.

Communication and literacy

Research on language development, speech, and communication has long been prioritized.

Topics including relationships, environment, and heredity were discussed at first. Both Piaget and Vygotsky, two researchers nowadays, have beliefs on children and language development. Focusing on the cognitive, Piaget also highlighted the significance of experiences and sentiments.

The zone of proximal development, inherited abilities, and models and mental structures based on learning were the main areas of concentration for Vygotsky. In addition to highlighting the significance of sociocultural settings, he also underlined how adults facilitate social relationships. Brodin's 1991 thesis, however, demonstrated that both are present in children with severe mental impairment.

The explanation of how children's communication develops is required as an addition. Several studies have reviewed the literature (Evans & Jones, 2007; Håland Anveden, 2017; Lennox, 2013; Saracho & Spodek, 2007), however additional study is still important based on more recent findings. In an editorial section on eloquence, speaking, and listening skills, Evans and Jones (2007) gathered 14 articles. Within the UK curriculum, oracy is a concept. Issues of second language learning, language acquisition in various cultural contexts, and pedagogical and theoretical issues are all highlighted in this text. UK studies speak about schooling for kids between the ages of five and six and seven and eight years. In Sweden, children ages one through five receive preschool education.

Effects of reading aloud and storytelling on children.

Early childhood educators frequently read aloud to their young charges multiple times a day because it is a recognized and beneficial practice. Children's literature read aloud promotes a love of books and reading as well as early literacy development, according to research. As they have an awareness of and liking for particular genres, many kids really start learning to read by responding to stories and books that are read aloud to them. A key component of creating a sense of community in the classroom is the use of literature by writers and artists who accurately represent a range of cultures. Readers' pleasure of books both now and in the future are influenced by the books that early childhood educators read aloud to their students. Children who learn to read on their own end up loving a lot of books and always ask to hear them again. Instructors must consider the purpose of each book they choose to read aloud as well as the lessons they want to get across. They cultivate children's literacy, empathy, and acceptance of themselves and others while supporting their own professional development as educators by carefully choosing the read-alouds they assign and stocking school libraries with them.

Conclusion

Our study demonstrates that narrative and aloud reading can be effective teaching strategies for young children. A well-planned approach functions as a tool for storytelling and read-alouds.

Despite not having this chance, preschool teachers stated that they recognized that storytelling and reading aloud were beneficial for fostering language and communication development. The concept cannot be put into practice until the significance of the study's findings

is known. A possible explanation for this could be that studies are frequently presented in foreign languages; time constraints are likely the other factor. Numerous researchers (e.g. Bruce, 2014; Norling and Lillvist, 2016 Wilson, 2011) recommend "early help before school to catch up with peers." It's crucial to remember that there are other strategies for promoting communication besides storytelling and reading aloud. In addition to the method of reading aloud and telling stories, didactic games and information technologies have a significant impact on the growth and development of knowledge skills in teaching English to preschool children.

REFERENCES

1. David A. J Eggen, P Kauchak. *Methods for Teaching: Promoting student learning* [M] 2002.
2. Liu Wang. *tomorrow xinglixue kaocha*[J]. 2017-18.
3. Feng Wang, *Applying Technology to Inquiry-Based Learning in Early Childhood Education*[J]. *Early Childhood Education*.
4. Brodin, J. (1991). *Att tolka barns signaler. Gravt utvecklingsstörda flerhandikappade barns lekoch kommunikation* [To interpret children's signals. Play and communication in children with profound and multiple disabilities] (Dissertation). Stockholm University, Department of education.
5. Sommer, D. (2012). *A childhood psychology: Young children in changing time*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
6. SOU, 2002: 27. *Mål i mun - Förslag till handlingsprogram för svenska språket* [Goals in mouth proposal for action program for Swedish language]. Stockholm: Ministry of Culture.